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EFFECTS OF SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SMALLHOLDER RICE FARMERS ON THE USE CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION STRATEGIES IN NORTH CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study evaluates how socioeconomic characteristics influence the adoption of climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder rice farmers in North Central Nigeria. A multistage sampling procedure selected 270 rice farmers, and data were collected using structured questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for data analysis. The findings indicate that the average age of respondents was 38 years, with the majority being male (71.10%), married (75.9%), and having an average household size of seven. Most respondents (91.80%) had formal education and were full-time rice farmers (74.0%) with an average of 13 years of experience, earning ₦142,185 annually from rice cultivation. Soil sustainability and land management strategies were the most widely adopted adaptation measures. A majority (87.8%) used herbicides, while 83.7% adopted improved rice varieties. Water storage was practiced by 66.3% of farmers, and 83.0% utilized weather forecasts. Access to credit facilities was reported by 67.8% and 81.5% engaged in off-farm employment for livelihood diversification. Factors such as educational level ($p < 0.05$), household size ($p < 0.01$), years of farming experience ($p < 0.01$), and occupation ($p < 0.1$) were found to significantly and positively influence the use of adaptation strategies. It is recommended that government policies on climate change adaptation should leverage farmers' existing knowledge and understanding of climate change.

Keywords: Socioeconomic Characteristics, Smallholder, rice, adaptation strategies, farmers

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Introduction

Agricultural productivity remains the primary source of livelihood for smallholder farmers. However, it is increasingly challenged by a changing climate. Climate is the principal determinant of agricultural activities, particularly crop production. Rainfall, a key indicator of climate change, is a critical climatic factor influencing the vulnerability of crop production; extremes in rainfall can result in either flooding or drought (Kumar and Sidane, 2018). Climate change (CC) refers to alterations in the state of the climate, identifiable by changes in the mean or variability of its properties that persist for decades or longer. These changes are primarily caused by human activities and natural forces, leading to increased levels of greenhouse gases in the Earth's atmosphere (IPCC, 2021). Climate change is now recognized as having a substantial impact on disaster management efforts and poses a significant threat to meeting the needs of vulnerable populations (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2021). Its widespread impacts include more frequent and severe heat waves, floods, droughts, storms, rising sea levels, and altered ecosystems. These changes can have severe consequences for food production, human health, economic stability, and environmental sustainability (Burke et al., 2022). Countries with economies that rely heavily on rain-fed and weather-sensitive agricultural production systems, such as Nigeria, are particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change. The vulnerability of a population is closely linked to its adaptive capacity, which provides a framework for enhancing resilience to environmental stress. Identifying both general and climate-specific elements of farmers' adaptation behaviors is essential to facilitate effective societal responses to predicted climate changes. For low-income countries like Nigeria, which are highly susceptible to climate change, understanding farmers' responses is crucial for designing appropriate adaptation strategies (IPCC, 2017). Prantilla and Laureto (2017) note that rice farming is threatened by climate change due to higher temperatures and shifting rainfall patterns. Acute water shortages and thermal stress may negatively impact rice productivity, while crop diseases such as rice blast and sheath and culm blight could become more prevalent.

Globally, rice is cultivated on more than 140 million hectares and is consumed more than any other cereal food (Rodenurg and Saito, 2022). It is among the three most important grain crops worldwide, with the capacity to meet global food needs (Wang et al., 2023). Rice is grown across Asia, America, Australia, Europe, and Africa (Chauhan et al., 2017). In Africa, rice has been cultivated for over 3,000 years and is grown in approximately 40 out of 54 countries. Its cultivation is the principal activity and primary source of income for more than 35 million smallholder rice farmers in Africa (Martins et al., 2021). Nigeria is the largest producer of rice in Africa and ranks as the 14th largest producer globally (Alih et al., 2021). In 2021, Nigeria produced an estimated 5.4 million metric tons of milled rice, which serves as a staple food for many Nigerians and provides raw materials for local industries. The largest quantities are produced in north-central Nigeria. Production increased from 5.5 million tonnes in 2015 to 5.8 million tonnes in 2017 (Abdulsalam and Adebayo, 2021). Rice remains a major staple food in the region and supports livelihoods for producers and those involved in value addition (Isonguyo et al., 2021). Annual rice demand in Nigeria has risen by 7.7%, while supply has grown at a slower rate of 5.5%, resulting in a demand-supply gap of 2.2%. This gap is attributed to challenges such as climate change and over-reliance on smallholder farmers (Onoja et al., 2024).

Addressing the challenges posed by climate change to rice production requires investigating how the socioeconomic characteristics of smallholder rice farmers influence their use of adaptation strategies. Understanding farmers' responses to climate change is essential for designing effective adaptation measures. With appropriate strategies in place, the adverse effects of climate change on rice production can be mitigated. Against this background, this study assessed the effects of socioeconomic characteristics on the use of climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder rice farmers in north-central Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: i. describe the socioeconomic characteristics of smallholder rice farmers in the study area; ii. determine the farmers' use of climate change adaptation strategies; and iii. examine the socioeconomic characteristics influencing the use of these strategies among farmers in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted in three north central states of Nigeria: Benue, Nasarawa, and Niger. This zone comprises Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau States, and the Federal Capital, Abuja. Geographically, the area is situated between longitudes 2°30' and 10°30' east of the Greenwich meridian and latitudes 6°30' and 11°20' north of the equator. The zone covers approximately 296,898 km², with a population of about 22,887,250 in 2016 and a projected population of 27,937,252 in 2024 (National Bureau Statistics (NBS), 2016). More than 40 ethnic groups reside in the zone. Over 77% of the population are rural dwellers, primarily engaged in agricultural activities. North central Nigeria shares borders with Cameroon to the northeast and Benin Republic to the northwest (Isonguyo et al., 2021). The region experiences two main seasons: the wet season, from late March to late October, and the dry season, from November to March. Annual rainfall ranges from 1,000 mm to 1,500 mm, with an average of 187 to 220 rainy days. Average monthly temperatures range from 21°C to 37°C. The zone's vegetation includes Forest Savannah Mosaic, Southern Guinea Savannah, and Northern Guinea Savannah. Major crops cultivated in the area are rice, maize, millet, sorghum, yam, potatoes, cassava, cowpea, soybean, vegetables, and fruits (Isonguyo et al., 2021).

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

The sample frame for this study comprised smallholder rice farmers in Benue, Nasarawa, and Niger States. A multistage sampling procedure combined with purposive selection was employed. In the first stage, three states (Benue, Nasarawa, and Niger) were purposively selected from six states in the zone, based on the intensity of rice production and the number of smallholder rice farmers. In the second stage, four out of fourteen major rice-producing Local Government Areas (LGAs) were selected in Benue, two out of six LGAs in Nasarawa, and three out of nine LGAs in Niger, resulting in a total of nine out of twenty-nine LGAs (30%) in the study area. The selected LGAs in Benue State were Guma, Tarka, Gwer East, and Gboko; in Nasarawa State, Doma and Lafia; and in Niger State, Katcha, Lavun, and Wushishi. The third stage involved selecting 24 villages out of 119 (20%), based on the high concentration of rice farmers. In the fourth stage, 270 respondents were randomly selected from the sample frame of 1,350 (20%) in the chosen villages, forming the study sample (Table 1).

Table 1: Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Selected States	Number of rice producing LGAs	Selected LGAs (30%)	Number of rice producing villages	Selected villages (20%)	Number of rice farmers
Benue	14	Guma	15	Abinsi	45
				Daudu	50
				Agasha	55
		Tarka	10	Akoodo	70
				Wannune	45
				Ikpayongo	35
		Gwer-east	13	Aghor	30
				Ahumbe	40
				Gboko	12
		Nasarawa	6	Lafia	13
Mbayion	25				
Niger	9	Katcha	12	Shabu	70
				Kwandere	100
				Gidan mai akuya	80
		Doma	15	Iwashi	95
				Alagye	50
				Doma	55
Niger	9	Katcha	12	Badeggi	60
				Katcha	50
		Lavun	13	Batage	50
				Mijin gari	60
				Ndaloke	40
Wushishi	15	Bankogi	65		
		Tungan kawo	45		
Total	29	9	119	24	1,350

Source: Reconnaissance survey, 2024.

Data Collection

Data for the study was obtained from primary and secondary sources. The former data was collected with the aid of structured questionnaires. The secondary information was obtained from survey data and some relevant literatures related to the study.

Data Analysis

Data obtained for this study were analyzed using descriptive (frequency count, percentage, mean) and Inferential (multiple regression analysis) statistics. Objectives ii were achieved using frequency counts and mean. Objective iii was achieved using multiple regression analysis.

Model specification

Multiple linear regression

The empirical model was specified as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + e$$

Where: Y_i = Climate change adaptation strategies (measured in number of strategies used)

β_0 = Constant

e = Error term

β_1 – β_{12} = the coefficients of the independent variables

X_1 = Age of the farmer (in years)

X_2 = Sex of the farmer (Male = 1 or female = 0)

- X₃ = Marital status (Married = 1, single = 0)
- X₄ = Household size (Number of persons in the household)
- X₅ = Educational status (Years spent in acquiring formal education)
- X₆ = Farming experience (in Years)
- X₇ = Farm size (in Hectares)
- X₈ = Rice income (₦ amount in naira)

Results and Discussion

Socioeconomic characteristics of smallholder rice farmers

Table 2 indicates that the mean ages of rice farmers were 39.23 years in Niger State, 36.79 years in Nasarawa State, and 36.36 years in Benue State. This suggests that Niger State had a relatively older population of rice farmers. The younger demographic in Benue and Nasarawa States may be more receptive to innovations, potentially enhancing their adaptive capacity (Ndamani and Shamsuddeen, 2018). Additionally, 71.1% of respondents were male, indicating that rice farming in these states is predominantly undertaken by men. This finding aligns with Yakubu et al. (2021), who reported that the agricultural sector and its labor-intensive activities are dominated by males. Furthermore, Table 2 shows that the majority (75.9%) of respondents were married.

This observation is consistent with Ogunniyi et al. (2021), who found that married households are predominantly engaged in farming. The mean household size also varies across states, with Niger State exhibiting the largest average household size. This may indicate that households in Niger State have greater labor resources for farming activities. Ndamani and Takeya (2022) reported that household size can influence farmers' decision-making. Table 2 further shows that the majority (74.0%) of respondents considered farming their primary occupation. The high proportion of full-time farmers highlights the need for sustainable agricultural practices and climate-resilient technologies to support their livelihoods. Abdulai et al. (2020) asserted that full-time farmers may require more intensive support and training in climate-resilient agricultural practices. Additionally, 98.7% of respondents in Benue State, 90.0% in Nasarawa State, and 86.6% in Niger State had attained primary, secondary, or tertiary education.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents according to Socioeconomic Characteristics (n =270)

Variables	Benue State (n=90)		Nasarawa State (n=90)		Niger State (n=90)	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Age (years)						
25-45	67	74.4	59	65.6	14	16.0
46-66	20	22.2	31	34.4	72	80.0
67-87	3	3.3	0	0.0	4	14.0
Mean		36.36		36.79		39.23
Sex						
Male	52	57.8	67	74.4	73	81.1
Female	38	42.2	23	25.6	17	18.9
Marital status						
Married	47	52.2	74	82.2	84	93.3
Single	28	31.1	10	11.1	3	3.3
Divorce	9	10.0	4	14.4	1	1.1
Widow	6	6.7	2	2.2	2	2.2
Household size (in number)						
0-5	61	67.8	49	54.4	21	23.33
6-11	15	16.7	30	33.3	47	52.22
12-17	4	4.4	5	5.6	19	21.11
18-23	8	8.9	6	6.7	2	2.22
>23	2	2.2	0	0.0	1	1.11
Mean		5.83		6.17		9.01
Occupation						
Full-time farmer	62	68.9	70	77.8	68	75.6
Part-time farmer	28	31.1	20	22.2	22	24.4
Educational attainment						
Informal education	1	1.1	9	10.0	12	13.3
Primary education	18	19.8	24	26.7	12	13.3
Secondary education	36	40.0	29	32.2	36	40.0
Tertiary education	35	38.9	28	31.1	30	33.3
Income from rice (₦)						
30000-100000	16	17.6	18	20.0	17	18.9
101000-171000	42	46.7	36	40.0	53	58.9
172000-242000	32	35.6	36	40.0	20	22.2
Mean		139772		149105		137677

Source: Field survey, 2024

This implies that Benue State had high percentage of educated farmers. This finding agrees with Adebayo *et al.* (2017) who stated that about 70% of the farmers in Adamawa State, Nigeria had some form of formal education. Also, Table 2 revealed the mean farming experience of 17.15 years, 14.29 years and 8.67 years for Niger, Nasarawa and Benue States respectively. This implies that, farmers in Niger State were more experienced in farming. Ousmanou and Alhaji (2017) found that years of farming experience induced farmers' decision to use responses to climate change. Table 2 showed that the overall mean rice income was ₦142,185. This implies that the farmers in the study area were averagely financially to cater for farm expenses. Ayanlade *et al.* (2017) reported that farmers with higher incomes may be more likely to adopt climate change adaptation strategies.

Use of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies

Table 3 revealed that soil and land management strategies were widely used. Majority (70.4%) of the farmers used hand weeding, 87.8% used herbicides and 68.9% used organic manure. This implies that the rice farmers in the study area depend on herbicides; hand weeding and organic manure as climate change adaptation strategies to curtail the impacts of climate change in their rice farms. According to Kumar *et al.* (2020) in a study on impact of climate change on rice production and adaptation strategies in India; stated that the widespread use of soil and land management strategies implies that the approach is effective and should be scaled up.

In Table 3 Majority (93.3%) of the farmers in Benue State, 82.2% in Nasarawa State and 75.6% in Niger State used improved crop varieties. This implies that Benue State uses improved rice varieties more than Nasarawa and Niger States. Similarly, majority (87.8%) in Niger State, 84.4% in Nasarawa State and 77.8% in Benue State used nursery bed. In the same vein, Niger State uses nursery bed in rice cultivation more than Benue and Nasarawa States. This implies that, crop specific innovation was commonly and widely used in the study area. Bello (2023) in a study on analysis on adaptation to climate change among rice farmers in Western Zone of Bauchi State, Nigeria; reported that the use of improve variety was a satisfying climate change adaptation strategies. It is recognized as a global leader in investment in smallholder agriculture, rural people, and rural communities, achieved by mobilizing and leveraging resources and by developing innovative financing mechanisms and instruments.

Table 3 revealed the overall (66.3%) of the farmers used water storage with 80.0% in Nasarawa, 77.8% in Niger and 41.1% in Benue States respectively. Similarly, majority (95.6%) of the farmers used irrigation in Niger, 57.8% in Benue and 33.3% in Nasarawa States respectively with overall 62.2% of the farmers. This implies that Water-linked management strategies were used by a significant proportion of farmers. Water storage was used most in Nasarawa State while irrigation was used most in Niger State. Having water storage system will avoid complete rice failure. This was in line with Yakubu *et al.* (2021) in a study on Assessment of perceived effects of climate change in rice production among farmers in North-west zone, Nigeria; who reported that the most significant climate change adaptation strategy used by farmers was water harvesting to improve soil moisture. Table 3 revealed the overall (83.0%) of the farmers used weather forecast with 86.7% in Benue, 84.4% in Nasarawa and 77.8% in Niger States respectively.

Table 3: Distribution of farmers according to use of climate change adaptation strategies (n=270)

Variable	Benue State (n=90)		Nasarawa State (n=90)		Niger State (n=90)		Pooled Sample (n=270)	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Soil and land management								
Sand filling	29	32.2	76	84.4	55	61.1	160	59.3
Hand weeding	84	93.3	74	82.2	50	55.6	208	77.0
Cultural control of pest	58	64.4	77	85.6	55	61.1	190	70.4
Use of organic manure	60	66.7	73	81.1	53	58.9	186	68.9
Use of herbicides	83	92.2	71	78.9	83	92.2	237	87.8
Family supplied labour	55	61.1	73	81.1	50	55.6	178	65.9

Crop specific innovation								
Improved crop varieties	84	93.3	74	82.2	68	75.6	226	83.7
Pest and diseases resistant varieties	49	54.4	77	85.6	81	90.0	207	76.7
Early maturing crop								
Changing planting dates	55	61.1	76	84.4	73	81.1	204	75.6
Use of nursery bed	61	67.8	72	80.0	72	80.0	205	75.9
	70	77.8	76	84.4	79	87.8	225	83.3
Water linked management								
Irrigation	52	57.8	30	33.3	86	95.6	168	62.2
Water storage	37	41.1	72	80.0	70	77.8	179	66.3
Climate information services								
Weather forecast	78	86.7	76	84.4	70	77.8	224	83.0
Extension services \	51	56.7	81	90.0	72	80.0	204	75.6
Training on climate change	50	55.6	40	41.4	64	71.1	154	57.0
Access to finance								
Access to credit facilities	37	41.1	82	91.1	64	71.1	183	67.8
Access to insurance services	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
Livelihood diversification								
Off-farm employment	64	71.1	79	87.8	77	85.7	220	81.5
Migration	36	40.0	82	91.1	57	63.3	175	64.8

Source: Field survey, 2024

Source: Field survey, 2024

Similarly, 90.0% of the farmers in Nasarawa, 80.0% in Niger and 56.7% in Benue States, used extension services with overall 75.6% of the farmers in the study areas. The rice farmers used weather forecast and extension services as climate change adaptation strategies in the study areas. The use of weather forecast by the rice farmers will enable the farmers to predict weather and its derivatives in order to plan and prepare with the appropriate climate change adaptation strategies ahead to avoid climate change effects on rice production. Nabara *et al.*(2023) in a study on Perception of Climate Change and Proposed Adaptation Strategies among Rice Farmers in North central Nigeria; reported that frequency of extension contacts to farmers during production plays a vital role on the level of accuracy and prediction of weather with respect to climate change.

Table 3 revealed that 91.1%, of the farmers in Nasarawa State, 71.1% in Niger State and 41.1% in Benue State used credit facilities. The farmers used credit facilities to harness their efforts in curtailing the effects of climate change. Fund is needed to purchase farm implements, farm inputs and other items necessary to negate the effects of climate change and improvement on livelihoods. This finding agrees with Alawode (2021) on income diversification and savings pattern among rural women in Oyo State, Nigeria; who stated that access to credit increases the farmers' investment in agricultural activities and livelihoods. Table 3 showed that majority (81.5%) of the farmers used off-farm employment proceeds to reduce the adverse effects of climate change on their rice production, with 87.8% in Nasarawa State, 85.7% in Niger State and 71.1% in Benue State. Similarly, 91.1% of the farmers in Nasarawa State, 63.3% in Niger State and 40.0% in Benue State used migration as climate change adaptation strategies in the study areas. This implies that livelihood diversification strategies were used by many rice farmers to reduce the effects of climate change and improve on their welfare. Yakubu *et al.* (2021) in a study on assessment of perceived effects of climate change in rice production among farmers in North-west zone, Nigeria; asserted that rural households in Nigeria engaged in different kinds of off-farm activities in order to supplement earnings from agriculture and family welfare.

Socioeconomic Characteristics influencing the use of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies

Regression analysis on the socioeconomic characteristics and the use of climate change adaptation strategies revealed the influence of independent variables on dependent variable among the smallholder rice farmers in the study area. The model explained ($R^2 = 0.800$) 80% of the variation in the use of climate change adaptation strategies attributed to independent variables.

Educational status and use of climate change adaptation strategies: Table 4 showed that educational status had positive coefficient and significantly ($\beta = 0.086$, $p < 0.05$) influenced the climate change adaptation strategies. This implies that as the years of formal education is increased, the use of climate change adaptation strategies increased. Therefore, educational status influences the adoption of climate change adaptation strategies. According to Yakubu *et al.*(2021) in a study on Assessment of perceived effects of climate change in rice production among farmers in North-west zone, Nigeria; reported that education influences high level of awareness and access to adaptation information

Household size and use of climate change adaptation strategies: Table 4 revealed that household size had positive coefficient and significantly ($\beta = 0.014$, $p < 0.01$) influenced the use of climate change adaptation strategies. This implies that as the household size increased the use of climate change adaptation strategies increased. Large family size influenced the farmers to embrace the adoption of climate change adaptation strategies. This could be as a result of many mouths to feed in the family. According to Nwaiwu *et al.* (2016) in a study on Climate Change Trend and Appropriate Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies in Southern Nigeria; who reported that increase in number of dependent contributes significantly to the use of climate change adaptation strategies

Table 4: Socioeconomic Characteristics influencing the use of climate change adaptation strategies

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Standardized error	Standardized coefficients (Beta)	t-ratio	p-value
(constant)	0.96	0.225		1.317	0.001
Age	-0.003	0.004	-0.055	-0.680	0.489
Sex	-0.014	0.074	-0.013	-0.286	0.853
Marital status	-0.017	0.044	-0.026	-0.377	0.714
Occupation	0.098	0.071	0.089	1.394	0.165
Educational level	0.007**	0.006	0.086	1.225	0.05
Household size	0.001***	0.007	0.014	0.180	0.01
Years of farming experience	0.008***	0.006	0.133	1.454	0.01
Farmland	0.024	0.028	-0.055	-0.849	0.397
$R^2 = 0.800$					
Adjusted $R^2 = 0.790$					

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Significant at 5%, *Significant at 1%.

Years of farming experience and use of climate change adaptation strategies: Multiple regression results in Table 4 showed that years of farming experience had positive coefficient and significantly ($\beta = 0.133$, $p < 0.01$) influenced the use of climate change adaptation strategies. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that increase in number of years influence the adoption of climate change adaptation strategies on rice production. This could be as a result of accumulated knowledge and experience on climate change acquired through the years. Akeem (2022) in a separate study on Climate Change Effects and Livelihood Adaptation Strategies by the Urban Poor in Ibadan, Nigeria; reported a significant relationship between years of farming experience and knowledge of climate change.

Conclusion

The smallholder rice farmers in north central, Nigeria are likely to be energetic, experienced and educated which could influence their ability to adapt to climate change and other challenges in rice farming.

The numerous adaptation strategies demonstrated shows the resourcefulness and adaptability of rice farmers in responding to climate change challenges.

The educational level, years of farming experience, household size and occupation as the socioeconomic characteristics that influenced farmers to use climate change adaptation strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were proposed:

1. Socioeconomic characteristics should be considered when promoting climate change adaptation strategies.
2. Develop climate change adaptation strategies that build on farmers' existing knowledge and understanding of climate change
3. Access to Finance: Improve access to financial services, including credit and insurance, to enable farmers to invest in their farms and manage climate-related risks.

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